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Cooch Behar, West Bengal

GEOGRAPHICAL APPRAISAL OF PURULIA DISTRICT USING REMOTE SENSING & GIS TECHNIQUES

Project report submitted by

GROUP - A (1st sem Certificate Course)

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GROUP - A

1 ST SEM, CERTIFICATE COURSE IN GEOINFORMATICS

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that GROUP - A, year of 2021, a student of the Certificate Course (1st Semester) in Geoinformatics in the academic session 2020-2021 has worked on the project entitled as “GEOGRAPHICAL APPRAISAL OF PURULIA DISTRICT USING REMOTE SENSING & GIS TECHNIQUES” under my supervision.

I wish him/her every success in life.

Mr. Abhijit Sen

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1. INTRODUCTION

Purulia District Overview

Purulia district, an integral part of Chhotanagpur plateau, is situated in the western part of West Bengal. It is present between 22° 42 and 23° 42 in north latitude and 85° 49 and 86° 54 in east longitude. The geographical area of the district is 6259 sq. km. The Bay of Bengal and the Hugli estuary are within 220 km from the centre of the district

The district headquarter is situated in Purulia town itself having three administrative sub – divisions and two agricultural sub – divisions having Headquarter one at Purulia town and another one at Raghunathpur. At present the district comprises 20 Community Development Blocks, 170 Gram Panchayats, 2,683 Mouzas.

1.1. History Of Purulia

Purulia is one of the oldest districts in West Bengal and has a rich culture and heritage to boast of. Encircled by Bankura, Midnapore and Burdwan districts of West Bengal and Hazaribag, Singbhum, Dhanbad, Ranchi, Jamshedpur and Bokaro districts of Jharkhand state, the place has undergone a lot of changes over the many years of its existence. From being a part of the country known as Vajra-bhumi to being a part of Jungle Mahals district and then Manbhum district, Purulia has seen a lot of phases in its life.

Pre Historic Times

Tagged as one of the oldest known districts known in West Bengal, Purulia has a rich culture and heritage to look back at. According to the Jaina Bhagavati-Sutra, the place existed as early as 5th century and was one of the 16 Mahajanapadas of its time. It is believed that Purulia was a part of the country known as Vajra-bhumi, in ancient times. However, apart from this, very little is known about the pre-historic era of Purulia.

Pre-Independence Era

It was during the British rule in India that Purulia gained importance. Just when British East-India Company acquired the 'Diwani' of Bengal, Bihar and Orissa, in the year 1765, Purulia achieved significance. In 1805, by the Regulation XVIII, a Jungle Mahals district, comprising of 23 parganas and mahals - including the present Purulia, was formed. However, years later, in 1833, the Jungle Mahals district was ruled out and a new district, by the name of Manbhum, was constituted, with headquarters at Manbazar.

Historical map of Manbhum district which the present Purulia district in West Bengal, and Dhanbad district and parts of Bokaro district in Jharkhand

Manbhum was extremely large in size and constituted of Bankura and Burdwan (in the present West Bengal), apart from Dhanbad, Dhalbhum, Saraikela and Kharswan (in the present Jharkhand and Orissa). In the year 1838, the district headquarters was shifted from Manbazar to Purulia (as it is known today). With this, Purulia was withdrawn from regular administration and placed under an officer called Principal Assistant (better known as Deputy Commissioner) to the agent of the Governor-General for South-Western Frontier.

Post-Independence Era

It was in 1956, nine years after India received its independence, that the district of Manbhum was partitioned and the states of West Bengal and Bihar were formed, under the States Reorganization Act and Transfer of Territories Act. In the November of 1956, Purulia was formed as one of the

GEOGRAPHICAL APPRAISAL OF PURULIA DISTRICT USING REMOTE SENSING & GIS TECHNIQUE

districts in West Bengal. Located at the westernmost side of the state, Purulia boasts of a tropical location. It acts as a funnel, transferring tropical monsoon current from the Bay of Bengal to the subtropical parts of northwest India. Purulia also acts as a gateway to reach the industrial belts of West Bengal and the hinterlands in Orissa, Jharkhand, Madhya Pradesh and Uttar Pradesh.

Farming

Purulia residents tending buffaloes and cows (1920)

GEOGRAPHICAL APPRAISAL OF PURULIA DISTRICT USING REMOTE SENSING & GIS TECHNIQUE

Purulia 1920

Classes for Christian baptism, Purulia

Purulia 1920

Classes for Christian baptism, Purulia

Planting out the seedlings, Purulia.

Source : https://leprosyhistory.org/geographical_region/site/purulia

1.2. ABOUT THE STUDY AREA

Purulia has its boundaries on the east with the Medinipur and Bankura Districts of West Bengal, in the North with the Burdwan district of West Bengal and the Dhanbad district of Jharkhand, on the north-west, west and south-west with the Hazaribagh, Ranchi and Singbhum District of Jharkhand. Apart of the northern boundary runs through the centre of the Panchet reservoir so that its water shared by the Dhanbad and Purulia. Similarly, the Eastern boundary runs partly through the centre of the Kangsabati reservoir. Latitudinal extension of the region is $85^{\circ} 43' E$ to $86^{\circ} 55' E$ and latitudinal extension is $22^{\circ} 38' N$ to $23^{\circ} 37' N$.

2. OBJECTIVE

- I. To study the general Physiographic characters of the study area.
- II. To study the Socio-Economic status of the local people.
- III. To prepare of Land Use Land Cover Map of the study area by Visual Interpretation.

DATABASE & SOFTWARE

Layers	Data	Website
True Colour Composite map	SENTINAL 2	https://eofactory.ai/
False Colour Composite map		https://eofactory.ai/
PURULIA Map Land Use Land Cover		https://eofactory.ai/
Soil		https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Soil-Map-of-Purulia-District
Socio- Economic aspect <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Population • Choropleth Map • Religion • Caste Composite • Literacy • Educational Status • Occupational Structure • Crop Production • Settlement & Communication • Tourism Language 		https://censusindia.gov.in/2011census/dchb/1914 PART B DCHB PURULIYA.pdf https://www.wikipedia.org/
COVID-19 Data		https://www.wbhealth.gov.in/

4. TRUE COLOUR COMPOSITE

A natural or true colour composite is a satellite image displaying a combination of the visible red, green and blue bands to the corresponding red, green and blue gun on the QGIS Software. Natural colour images can be low in contrast and somewhat hazy due the scattering of blue light by the atmosphere.

5. FALSE COLOUR COMPOSITE

False colour composites allow us to visualize the wavelengths the human eye does not see (near the infrared range). ... false colour images are a representation of a multispectral image created using ranges other than visible red, green and blue, such as red, green and blue image components.

6. ADMINISTRATIVE SET UP :

(i) Region of the state where district is located :

Puruliya district lies in the extreme western part of the state. The northern, western and southern part of the district is bounded by the state of Jharkhand. The eastern part is bounded by the districts of Bardhaman, Bankura and Paschim Medinipur.

(ii) Total number of C.D. Blocks :

The district of Puruliya has three Sub-divisions namely (a) Puruliya Sadar (East) (b) Puruliya Sadar (West) and (c) Raghunathpur. There are a total of 21 Police Stations in the district. Puruliya Sadar (East) Sub-division consists of 8 Police Stations namely Bandowan, Hura, Manbazar, Puncha, Boro, Kenda, Puruliya Town and Puruliya Muffassil. Puruliya Sadar (West) Sub-division consists of 7 Police Stations namely Arsha, Baghmundi, Balarampur, Barabazar, Jaypur, Jhalda and Kotshila. Raghunathpur Subdivision consists of 6 Police Stations namely Kashipur, Neturia, Para, Santaldih, Raghunathpur, and Santuri

The district is divided into 20 Community Development (C.D.) Blocks. Puruliya Sadar (East) Sub-division consists of 7 C.D. Blocks namely Bandowan, Hura, Manbazar-I, Manbazar-II, Puncha, Puruliya-I and Puruliya-II. Puruliya Sadar (West) Sub-Division consists of 7 C.D. Blocks namely Arsha, Baghmundi, Balarampur, Barabazar, Jaypur, Jhalda-I and Jhalda-II. Raghunathpur Sub-division consists of 6 C.D. Blocks namely Kashipur, Neturia, Para, Raghunathpur-I, Raghunathpur-II and Santuri.

(iii) Total number of Towns/Villages :

The district has 28 urban units, out of which 3 are Municipalities and 25 are Census Towns. Raghunathpur (M), Jhalda (M) and Puruliya (M) are the names of 3 Municipalities. The names of 25 Census Towns are Jaypur, Raghampur (P), Santaldih Thermal Power Project–Town, Kanki (P), Dubra, Chapari, Shankara, Nabagram, Arra, Saltor, Hijuli, Par Beliya, Murulia, Kantaranguri (P), Lapara, Lagda, Chekya, Begun Kodar, Balarampur, Barabazar, Manbazar, Adra, Jhalda (P), Hutmura and Bandoan. The district consists of 170 Gram Panchayats covering 2,667 villages.

7. PHYSIOGRAPHY

7.1. PURULIA AS A PART OF CHOTA-NAGPUR PLATEAU

In the lowest step of the Chota Nagpur Plateau, the Manbhum area covers the present Purulia district in West Bengal, and Dhanbad district and parts of Bokaro district in Jharkhand, and the Singhbhum area broadly covers Kolhan division of Jharkhand. The Manbhum area has a general elevation of about 300 metres (1,000 ft) and it consists of undulating land with scattered hills – Baghmundi and Ajodhya range, Panchakot and the hills around Jhalda are the prominent ones. Adjacent Bankura district of West Bengal has been described as the “connecting link between the plains of Bengal on the east and Chota Nagpur plateau on the west. The same could be said of the Asansol and Durgapur subdivisions of Bardhaman district.

Map of the Chota Nagpur

Joychandi Pahar in Purulia district in West Bengal

Location : Jharkhand,Bihar ,Chhattisgarh, Odisha and West Bengal

Sal trees found in forests of Chota Nagpur Plateau

Landscape and topography of Purulia

Source: Wikipedia (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Chota_Nagpur_Plateau)

7.2. TOPOGRAPHY :

The topographical feature shows gradual decent from the uneven Chhota Nagpur plateau to the plain land of the state in the east. The district of Puruliya is divided into three sub-micro regions on the basis of elevation and the nature of topography, viz. 1) Damodar–Darkeshwar Upland, 2) Upper Kasai Basin, and 3) Bagmundi–Bundwan Upland

3D TOPOGRAPHY VIEW OF PURULIA DISTRICT
(Source: www.ijsrp.org Publications, Volume 6, Issue 9, September 2016)

1) Damodar–Darkeshwar Upland : This region lies in the north–east of the district bordering Jharkhand (erstwhile Bihar) to the north, West and South. The area becomes undulating with hillocks of hard rocks, which are extended from the high plateau of Central India and Chota Nagpur. There are some hills ranging from 150 to 750 meters approximately in altitude.

2) Upper Kasai Basin : The region extends in the central part of the district, where the Kasai river flows. The region has undulating land but in the lower part, there are degraded low lands. The elevation rises from 200 to 300 metres and its general slope is from West to East and South–east.

3) Bagmundi–Bandwan Upland : This region lies over the north–western and the Southern portion of the district. It is a highland area descending from the Ranchi plateau. At some places the high lands are very steep and crisscrossed by the streams. In Bagmundi and Balarampur areas, the Ayodhya Range forms the main high lands. It acts

like the watershed for both Kasai and Subarnarekha. The elevation ranges from 475 to 700 meters approximately. The soils of the region are red sandy, red loamy and alluvial. The elevation of the district from main sea level is 677 metres.

7.3. FLORA & FAUNA :

The species of flora is predominant in the plateau area of Puruliya. Trees like *Palas*, *Kul*, *Mahul*, *Kenod*, *Bhela*, *Dha*, *Pial*, *Arjun*, *Asan*, *Chhatui* etc. are found in numbers. Some of these trees bear both grand looking flowers and sweet fruits. In the forest *Sal*, *Karum*, *Sisha*, *Gumhar*, *Akashmani*, *Kusum*, Eucalyptus, Fig, Banyan, various bushes and herbs are found. Now-a-days wastelands are being brought under the green shed of various classes of plants by the Forest Department and the Panchayat functionaries. As regards the species of fauna in the district, they are Elephant, found in the *jungles* (forests) of Ayodhya Region, Bundwan and Kuilapal. Besides Elephants, the forest of Puruliya is also the wild abode of Bear, Wolf, Hyaena, Wild Hog, Rabbit, Deer, Monkey, Bush Cat, Jackal, Fox etc. The abode of Avis are in the stones groves of Agodya, Jaichandi Phar, Panchet and Vultures, Falcon, Kite, Owl, Bat, Peacock, Wild Crow, Dove, Wild Fowl, Rose band, Parrot, Cuckoo, Sparrow and many other birds are found in the forest trees spread over the entire district. Migratory birds are also seen on the quiet watery, greenery spots in the winter season.

7.4. GEOLOGY:

The district embraces diverse groups of rocks of various geological ages ranging from Archaean to recent viz. The Chotonagpur Gneissic complex covers most parts of the district. Plutonic Gabbro and orthositic rocks, meta-sedimentaries and meta basics of Singbhum groups Dalma group of basic volcanic rocks, Intrusive granites. The Gondwana group has sedimentary with coal seam and quaternary sedimentary as in an order of decreasing antiquity. There are two shared zone

- a) South Purulia share zone –WNW-ESE trending tectonically disturbed share zone.
- b) North Purulia share zone .

7.5. CLIMATE:

The climate of the area is characterized by hot summer and well distributed seasonal rainfall. The year may be divided into four seasons .The cold season starts by about the middle of November and continues till the end of February. The hot season which extends up to May .The southwestern monsoon season continues the end of September , October and the first day of November constitute the past monsoon season.

7.6. TEMPERATURE:

Temperature rises rapidly about from early March .May is the hottest month with a mean delay temp.35.6°C on exceptional day of May and June day temp rise up to 42°C. January is the coldest month the maximum temp of 25.3°C and minimum 12.4°C. During the assuage of western distribution areas the north India a cold weather is experienced with a minimum temp of 5°-6°C at night .From November to mid-February the days are quite pleasant but the nights are cold so an extremity temp is found Rainfall. The average annual rainfall 1300mm the cold and hot weather raise are very light. The annual rainfall about 85% of Rainfall occurs during June to September constitute. August is the wettest month of the year .

7.7. RELATIVE HUMIDITY:

Relative humidity is high during the monsoon season being generally between -75%-85% after the withdraw of south-west monsoon relative humidity decreases gradually .During the hot season, the dissent part of the year it stays between 25-35%.

7.8. SOIL TYPE:

The soil type of the area under study may be devised into two main categories- a)The laterite soil of the hilly area ,this own its origin to the hot and humid climate associated with an alternate period of the wet and dry season. These are residual soil, formed of the bed rock of granite and genie. Decomposed and designated rocks have formed the soil and their rem in-situ, geologically their soil are older but immature compared to the alluvium of the foot hill area. Ecological they are however old enough to support plants. When under the forest canopy, sheltered from direct exposure to erosion the soil get enriched by chemical decomposition of present materials and organic matter and develop into natural soil. But as soon the vegetation cover is removed the soil is severely depleted by mechanical weathering and erosion. These soils are mostly developed from gneiss. They are usually very shallow ,well drained, gravelly, loamy to the gravelly loamy surface they developed as a result of leaching of calcium from upper horizon due to heavy and concentration of iron calcium at or near the surface of the soil .The colour of the soil varies from light red to brown depending on the minerals matter. Only in the river bed, there is the concentration of fine loamy of darker. In Purulia the soil is lightly textured with high porosity and poor water holding capacity. In the district of Purulia more than 24000 ha of land have been converted to culture able wasteland.

GEOGRAPHICAL APPRAISAL OF PURULIA DISTRICT USING REMOTE SENSING & GIS TECHNIQUE

Source: Wikipedia (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Purulia>)

7.9. RIVERS AND LAKES:

Several rivers flow across Purulia district. Among these Kangsabati, Kumari, Silabati (silai), Dwarakeswar, Subarnarekha and Damodar are the important ones. Although several rivers flows across the district, 50% of the water run off due to the undulated topography. There are also several Small dams like Futiyary, Murguma, Pardi, Burda, Gopalpur, which are mainly used for irrigation of agriculture field. Saheb Bandh is one of the popular and famous waterbodies of Purulia. It is located in the heart of the purulia town. It is a shelter of the migratory birds which comes from Bangladesh, Burma, Sindh, Baluchistan during December to March.

7.10. NATURAL VEGETATION:

The natural vegetation of the area under study like Purulia district as a whole is an arboreal type. The hilly part of the study area is still now under forest coverage. The large gregarious, Sal is the most predominant forest tree. There are two varieties of sal the most prevalent, having dark brown heart wood while that the Dom sal, of the lower hills so white slightly tinged with red. Other than Sal Muchkunda a tall evergreen tree, the tall and shady Shimul and Palash is also found. Mauha is also an important tree of this region. In the wood land there is the thick cover of greens and other a layer of shrubs beneath the level

of the forest foliage depending on the subtle variation. There is also a protected forest called Matha protected forest covers the Matha pahar between Kestobazar and Kathlajal through forest cover has, however, being cleared and degraded or replaced by shrubs, bushes, and cultivated fields at the foot hil plains. It was indeed a part of the jungle mahal, a land of tropical deciduas forest due to biotic interference such as shifting cultivation, fire, graze ring and also unscientific forest management.

8. LAND USE LAND COVER MAP

The terms land use and land cover are often used interchangeably, but each term has its own unique meaning. Land cover refers to the surface cover on the ground like vegetation, urban infrastructure, water, bare soil etc. Identification of land cover establishes the baseline information for activities like thematic mapping and change detection analysis. Land use refers to the purpose the land serves, for example, recreation, wildlife habitat, or agriculture. When used together with the phrase Land Use / Land Cover (LULC) generally refers to the categorization or classification of human activities and natural elements on the landscape within a specific time frame based on established scientific and statistical methods of analysis of appropriate source materials.

Land cover is the physical material at the surface of the earth. Land use is the description of how people utilize the land for the socio-economic activities.

Total Agricultural land - 197.52 sqkm,
 Total Vegetation area - 999 sqkm,
 Total Dense forest Area - 706.85 sqkm,
 Railway length – 307 km,
 NH & SH – 513 km,
 Total Local length - 920.165 km,
 Total Fallow Land - 1695.48 sq Km.

9. SOCIO- ECONOMIC:

9.1. DEMOGRAPHY ASPECT

The spatial distribution of population is one of the most important topics of Human Geography. It is significantly important, because man has brought tremendous change over the earth surface. Man being a single most important powerful geographical factor transforming the earth surface with scientific and technological achievements.

Purulia is constituted by plateaus, plains with terraces, scarps, inselbergs, which is evolved under polycyclic evolution.

9.2. AREA OF PURULIA

Area of Purulia is 6259 Sq. Km. It is 5th largest district in West Bengal and 161th largest in India in terms of total area.

9.3. POPULATION OF PURULIA

Purulia district is located in West Bengal . Population of Purulia district is 2927965 as per Census 2011. Purulia is 16th most Populous district out of total 19 districts in West Bengal and it is 129th most Populous district in India. The population density of Purulia is 468 Persons per square Km. It is 19th most densely populated out of 19 districts in West Bengal and it is 265th most densely populated district out of total 640 districts in India.

9.4. DENSITY OF POPULATION

The density of Puruliya district in 2011 is 468 people per sq. km. In 2001, Puruliya district density was at 405 people per sq. km. Puruliya district administers 6,259 square kilometers of areas.

BLOCK NAME	POPULATION DENSITY	BLOCK NAME	POPULATION DENSITY
Arsha	412	Manbazar I	404
Baghmundi	317	Manbazar II	339
Balaramur	458	Neturia	533
Bandwan	270	Para	642
Barabazar	407	Puncha	375
Hura	375	Purulia I	537
Jaipur	595	Purulia II	547
Jhalda I	435	Raghunathpur I	583
Jhalda II	577	Raghunathpur II	576
Kashipur	443	Santuri	437

Source : Census 2011

9.5. RURAL - URBAN POPULATION

As per 2011 census, 87.26 % population of Puruliya districts lives in rural areas of villages. The total Puruliya district population living in rural areas is 2,556,801 of which males and females are 1,304,208 and 1,252,593 respectively. In rural areas of Puruliya district, sex ratio is 960 females per 1000 males. If child sex ratio data of Puruliya district is considered, figure is 956 girls per 1000 boys. Child population in the age 0-6 is 365,161 in rural areas of which males were 186,695 and females were 178,466. The child population comprises 14.31 % of total rural population of Puruliya district. Literacy rate in rural areas of Puruliya district is 62.73 % as per census data 2011. Gender wise, male and female literacy stood at 76.83 and 48.06 percent respectively. In total, 1,374,860 people were literate of which males and females were 858,620 and 516,240 respectively.

id	NAME	RURAL	URBAN
1	NETURIA	83137	18290
2	R.N. PUR-II	107827	5963
3	SANTURI	72586	5929
4	R.N. PUR-I	96488	21272
5	PARA	167997	32624
6	KASHIPUR	174325	25758
7	HURA	143575	0
8	PURULIA-II	157862	11626
9	PURULIA-I	145494	5694
10	PUNCHA	123855	0
11	JOYPUR	123090	10259
12	JHALDA-II	135814	12342
13	JHALDA-I	127759	9384
14	BAGHMUNDI	135579	0
15	ARSHA	154736	0
16	BALARAMPUR	113519	24431
17	BARABAZAR	162508	8056
18	MANBAZAR-I	144550	9521
19	MANBAZAR-II	97164	0
20	BUNDWAN	88936	5993

9.5.1. LEVEL OF URBANIZATION

In this figure, we try to give a concept about level of urbanization by using choropleth method and compare the percentage of urban population of 2001 and 2011 by bar diagram. Levels of urbanization of five blocks are zero and they are Ashra, Bagmundi, Hura, Puncha, and Manbazar-II, where not an urban center has been grown. Only two blocks are almost equal to the national and state average they are Purulia-II and Raghunathpur-I. Bar diagram (fig. no.-2) clearly show that the Purulia-II and Raghunathpur-I has highest concentrate of urban population. Many of the blocks newly set up their urban areas which are Jaipur, Jhalda-II, Purulia-I, Manbazar-I, Bandoan, and Santuri in the last census 2011. One of the most important things is found, there the urban populations of some blocks are decreasing and they are Raghunathpur-I & II and Balarampur

id	NAME	URBANISATION IN 2001	URBANISATION IN 2011
1	NETURIA	14.23	18.03
2	R.N. PUR-II	5.7	5.24
3	SANTURI	0	7.55
4	R.N. PUR-I	19.2	18.06
5	PARA	6.83	16.26
6	KASHIPUR	11.78	12.87
7	HURA	0	0
8	PURULIA-II	0	6.86
9	PURULIA-I	0	3.77
10	PUNCHA	0	0
11	JOYPUR	0	7.69
12	JHALDA-II	0	8.33
13	JHALDA-I	0	6.84
14	BAGHMUNDI	0	0
15	ARSHA	0	0
16	BALARAMPUR	18.48	17.71
17	BARABAZAR	5.15	4.72
18	MANBAZAR-I	0	6.18
19	MANBAZAR-II	0	0
20	BUNDWAN	0	6.31

9.6. SEX-RATIO OF PURULIA

With regards to Sex Ratio in Puruliya, it stood at 957 per 1000 male compared to 2001 census figure of 954. In 2011 census, child sex ratio is 953 girls per 1000 boys compared to figure of 964 girls per 1000 boys of 2001 census data.

id	NAME	TOTAL POPULATION	MALE	FEMALE
1	NETURIA	101427	52310	49117
2	R.N. PUR-II	113790	58568	55222
3	SANTURI	78515	40085	38430
4	R.N. PUR-I	117760	60897	56863
5	PARA	200621	103306	97315
6	KASHIPUR	200083	101801	98282
7	HURA	143575	72867	70708
8	PURULIA-II	169488	86462	83026
9	PURULIA-I	151188	77858	73330
10	PUNCHA	123855	62676	61179
11	JOYPUR	133349	68977	64372
12	JHALDA-II	148156	75453	72703
13	JHALDA-I	137143	70095	67048
14	BAGHMUNDI	135579	69520	66059
15	ARSHA	154736	78398	76338
16	BALARAMPUR	137950	70995	66955
17	BARABAZAR	170564	86353	84211
18	MANBAZAR-I	154071	78039	76032
19	MANBAZAR-II	97164	48943	48211
20	BUNDWAN	94929	47798	47131

Source: Purulia District hand book, Census-2011

9.7. LITERACY RATE

Average literacy rate of Puruliya in 2011 were 64.48 compared to 55.57 of 2001. If things are looked out at gender wise, male and female literacy were 77.86 and 50.52 respectively. For 2001 census, same figures stood at 73.72 and 36.50 in Puruliya District. Total literate in Puruliya District were 1,624,905 of which male and female were 1,002,058 and 622,847 respectively. In 2001, Puruliya District had 1,182,284 in its district.

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id	NAME	RURAL	URBAN	LITERATES	ILLITERATES
1	NETURIA	83137	18290	57174	44253
2	R.N. PUR-II	107827	5963	65936	47854
3	SANTURI	72586	5929	43604	34911
4	R.N. PUR-I	96488	21272	69408	48352
5	PARA	167997	32624	112377	88244
6	KASHIPUR	174325	25758	125307	74776
7	HURA	143575	0	86067	57508
8	PURULIA-II	157862	11626	91314	78174
9	PURULIA-I	145494	5694	83688	67500
10	PUNCHA	123855	0	73486	50369
11	JOYPUR	123090	10259	65044	68305
12	JHALDA-II	135814	12342	67532	80624
13	JHALDA-I	127759	9384	76973	60170
14	BAGHMUNDI	135579	0	64939	70640
15	ARSHA	154736	0	70413	84323
16	BALARAMPUR	113519	24431	71176	66774
17	BARABAZAR	162508	8056	92837	77727
18	MANBAZAR-I	144550	9521	85654	68417
19	MANBAZAR-II	97164	0	51425	45739
20	BUNDWAN	88936	5993	50810	44119

Source: Purulia District hand book, Census-2011

9.8. RELIGION:

According to the Purulia District 2011 census, Hindus numbered 80.56% of the population. Christians numbered 5.04% of the population. Muslims numbered 11.17% of the population. Others numbered rest of the population. Hinduism is the dominant religion in Purulia 74% followers.

9.9. CASTE

About 51.09 % of the populations are males and 48.91% are female. The percentage of Scheduled Caste and Scheduled Tribes are 19.38% and 18.45%.

Total numbers households in SECC Census 2011 is 536972. Total Households considered for deprivation is 437234.

id	NAME	SC	ST
1	NETURIA	29.7	25.29
2	R.N. PUR-II	36.66	6.75
3	SANTURI	27.25	34.56
4	R.N. PUR-I	39.4	12.95
5	PARA	37	5.53
6	KASHIPUR	29.45	27.94
7	HURA	19.52	25.46
8	PURULIA-II	26.45	5.13
9	PURULIA-I	16	8.7
10	PUNCHA	14.54	24.74
11	JOYPUR	13.41	10.31
12	JHALDA-II	9.13	13.77
13	JHALDA-I	12.53	12.14
14	BAGHMUNDI	10.36	25.11
15	ARSHA	11.82	21.69
16	BALARAMPUR	11.15	37.32
17	BARABAZAR	6.83	20.23
18	MANBAZAR-I	22.15	23.42
19	MANBAZAR-II	6.51	48.97
20	BUNDWAN	5.15	54.88

Source: Purulia District hand book, Census-2011

10. ECONOMIC ASPECT

10.1. OCCUPATIONAL STRUCTURE

Main working class has been decreased from 25.43 % in 2001 census to 20.93 % in 2011 census whereas Marginal working class has been increased from 19.03 % in 2001 to 21.71 % in 2011 census. Cultivators have been shifted to other working classes.

id	NAME	CULTIVATORS	AGRICULTURAL LABOURERS	HOUSEHOLD INDUSTRY WORKERS	OTHER WORKERS
1	NETURIA	15.17	24.79	2.9	57.14
2	R.N. PUR-II	13.89	30.07	3.12	52.93
3	SANTURI	21.28	33.36	3.37	41.98
4	R.N. PUR-I	13.98	29.64	3.55	52.83
5	PARA	16.95	35.34	3.34	44.37
6	KASHIPUR	18.32	43.68	2.97	35.03
7	HURA	25.06	50.31	2.53	22.1
8	PURULIA-II	17.58	37.38	5.89	39.15
9	PURULIA-I	21.04	39.3	3.61	36.05
10	PUNCHA	38.51	36.63	2.07	22.79
11	JOYPUR	29.47	30.07	12.43	28.02
12	JHALDA-II	15.83	15.07	48.15	20.94
13	JHALDA-I	30.38	35.18	9.91	24.53
14	BAGHMUNDI	27.45	47.93	2.12	22.5
15	ARSHA	27.08	41.33	12.61	18.98
16	BALARAMPUR	21.76	37.73	2.68	37.83
17	BARABAZAR	28.6	50.04	2.89	18.47
18	MANBAZAR-I	18.83	59.08	2.88	19.21
19	MANBAZAR-II	26.93	62.28	1.82	8.97
20	BUNDWAN	18.47	52.4	10.08	19.06

Source: Purulia District hand book, Census-2011

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id	NAME	MAIN WORKERS	MARGINAL WORKERS	NON-WORKERS
1	NETURIA	19.13	17.62	63.25
2	R.N. PUR-II	17.39	18.74	63.87
3	SANTURI	19.47	18.08	62.45
4	R.N. PUR-I	19.7	14.34	65.96
5	PARA	18.2	17.82	63.99
6	KASHIPUR	18.74	22.74	58.52
7	HURA	22.16	26.35	51.5
8	PURULIA-II	18.47	22.96	58.57
9	PURULIA-I	18.36	22.3	59.34
10	PUNCHA	24.11	28.4	47.49
11	JOYPUR	19.12	19.63	61.25
12	JHALDA-II	28.91	16.43	54.66
13	JHALDA-I	21.92	19.07	59.01
14	BAGHMUNDI	20.02	26.63	53.36
15	ARSHA	22.43	25.06	52.5
16	BALARAMPUR	20.83	20.25	58.92
17	BARABAZAR	23.21	26.22	50.57
18	MANBAZAR-I	17.48	30.47	52.05
19	MANBAZAR-II	21.41	31.58	47.01
20	BUNDWAN	20.46	29.47	50.07

Source: Purulia District hand book, Census-2011

10.2. CROP PRODUCTION

Cultivation of this district is predominantly mono-cropped. About 60 % of the total cultivated land is upland. Out of the total agricultural holding about 73 % belongs to small and marginal farmers having scattered and fragmented smallholding. Paddy is the primary crop of the district. 57 % of the total land is under net-cropped area and only 15 % of the net cropped area is under multi crop cultivation. 83 % of the net-cropped area is under Kharif paddy cultivation. Cropping intensity is 114.59. The crops are grown mostly under rainfed condition, generally with low fertilizer consumption per unit area Thus per hectare production is also low as compared to other districts of West Bengal.

10.3. FISHERIES

The production of fish in this district is not much encouraging though a large no. of tanks both under Govt. & Private sector are there. If these tanks are utilised properly for Pisciculture and Duck rearing, the production of fish as well as eggs will be increased to a considerable extent thereby increasing the scope of income & employment to the rural people. Annual inland production of fish of the district is 48,928 MT. So, there is an ample possibility to bring more area under efficient pisciculture.

Area available for Pisciculture - 16214 Ha.

Dam and Reservoir - 8507.74 Ha.

Pond - 18575.69 Ha.

10.4. IRRIGATION

Total net irrigated land of this district is 87816 Ha., which is 21.57 % of the gross cropped area. There is altogether 32 Nos. of medium irrigation Schemes in this district. Out of these schemes, 26 are completed and 6 are in various stages of execution.

11. TRANSPORT :

Though situated 330 km. away from the state capital Kolkata, the district is well connected through express highways and railways. The district has express connectivity with most of the major towns and cities, not only within West Bengal but also with other cities viz. Mumbai, Ranchi, Patna, New Delhi, Chennai and others. The road transport plays as an important transportation medium of the district. The road transport is adequate in terms of bus availability and goods flow. National Highway 32 (NH-32) connects this district with Jamshedpur, Bokaro, Dhanbad and others. NH-60A connects Puruliya with State Highway-9 (SH-9) at Bankura and subsequently to NH-2 at Durgapur. SH-5 also plays important role in district's transport network as it connects the towns like Raghunathpur, Adra, Santaldih and Neturia to NH-2 at Neamatpur and Asansol. Puruliya has excellent road connectivity with Raniganj-Asansol industrial belt. South Bengal State Transport Corporation also runs buses from Puruliya to Kolkata via SH-5 thus connecting towns and cities like Raghunathpur, Adra, Neturia to the industrial belt of Asansol, Raniganj, Durgapur, Burdwan and others. There are also many private bus operators on this route.

Frequent express and mail train services are also available in the district. The district is served by three rail connections provided by the South Eastern Railways. One line runs from Jharkhand in the South through the district up to Asansol passing through Adra Division. Another line runs between Bankura and Dhanbad also via the Adra Division. The third line connects Puruliya with Jharkhand. Major cities and towns like Ranchi, Tatanagar, Patna, Howrah, Dhanbad, Asansol, Bhubaneswar, Durgapur, Mumbai, Chennai and New Delhi are now well connected with the district as most of the major trains stop at Puruliya Junction Railway Station which is on the Asansol-Tatanagar-Kharagpur line and is about 1.5 km. from the town centre. Most of the long distance trains stop in this railway station viz. Purushottam Express, Samarsata Express, Guwahati-Chennai Express, Porbandar-Santragachi Express etc. There is a link railway to Kolkata via Bardhaman, Adra, Puruliya and Tata. Trains like Rupashi Bangla, Lalmati Express, Puruliya Express runs between Puruliya and Howrah via Kharagpur.

12. CULTURE

Purulia has rich cultural heritage. It has the mixed culture of Bengal, Jharkhand, and Orissa as it was a part of these areas for various times. From archaeological evidences to local festivals, every cultural event has got a tribal touch in it, which is the speciality of Purulia. Living mostly in rural areas and keeping intact many of their socio-cultural values, more or less in pristine forms, the rural people of Purulia have their folks to speak about many of their tenets. The distinctiveness of those is well demonstrated with the sentiments and feelings of the population and these are marked with splash of colours and often entwined with pathos, romanticism, velour and social consciousness. Purulia got a distinct folk culture of Jhumur, Tusu, Bhadu songs. It is also the birthplace of a martial dance of Bengal [Chhau](#).

13. LANGUAGE:

14. TOURISM:

Tourism is another source of income for this district. Forests, Hillocks, Rivulets, Streams, Wild Life, Flora & Fauna has tremendous scope to be explored by the tourist. The prominent of the district like Ajodhya Hills, Matha, Murguma Dam and Kuilapal Forests, Jaychandi Pahar, Panchakote Raj, Duarsini Hills and Forests attract quite a good number of visitors to Purulia every year.

Some Tourist Spots in Purulia:

1. Joychandi Pahar
2. Ajodhya Hills
3. Saheb Bandh
4. Gajaburu Hills
5. Doldanga
6. Branti reservoir or Muradi lake
7. Cheliama
8. Surulia
9. Murugama Dam

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15. MOST RECENT COVID-19 DATA OF PURULIA :

COVID-19 DATA OF PURULIA OF 2 CONSECUTIVE YEARS				
YEAR	TOTAL CASES	TOTAL DISCHARGED	TOTAL DEATHS	TOTAL ACTIVE CASES
31 st MAY ,2020	7	0	0	7
31 st MAY 2021	15613	14974	107	532

Here we are showing the burning health issues data through GIS technique that is covid 19 pandemic data. In 1st June 2020 total no. of case in Purulia is 7 where 1st June 2021 total cases increased 18693, Total discharged 18091, Total death 108, Total Active cases 570.

16. CONCLUSION

Purulia lies between 22.60 degrees and 23.50 degrees north latitudes and 85.75 degrees and 86.65 degrees east longitudes. The geographical area of the district is 6,259 km² (2,417 sq mi).

Purulia is the westernmost district of West Bengal with all-India significance because of its tropical location, its shape as well as function like a funnel. It funnels not only the tropical monsoon current from the Bay to the subtropical parts of north-west India, but also acts as a gateway between the developed industrial belts of West Bengal and the hinterlands in Orissa, Jharkhand, Madhya Pradesh and Uttarpradesh. Several rivers flow across Purulia district. Kangsabati, Kumari, Silabati (silai), Dwarakeswar, Subarnarekha and Damodar are the important rivers. Although several rivers flows across the district, 50% of the water run off due to the undulated topography. For its convenient location, this place has acquired an important place in the tourist map in India.

The physiographic character of Purulia District is being posted with the help of QGIS Software adding various colours which allows us to visualize the wavelengths the human eye does not see. Land use propose the purpose of land serves for example, recreation, wildlife habitat or agriculture and the ground covers like urban infrastructure, vegetation, water, bare soil, etc.

Last but not the least, Purulia is rich in humanity where all the people and other living live under one blanket, they respect each other either say in religion or caste or classes. Tourists are welcomed with open arms and huge smile and also can magnify their reflection of good and happy life.

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